

Drought resistance

Screening advanced breeding lines and germplasm for drought resistance under upland conditions

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We screened 180 germplasm and advanced breeding lines involving parents of indica-japonica types under direct-seeded upland conditions at Krishnagar (gangetic alluvial zone) during the summer season (May-Jun). Short-duration lines are preferred for this season, since the monsoon generally appears about the third week of Jun. Short duration also gives room for the subsequent wet season crop.

Soil of the experimental plot had light medium texture with moderate sloping (susceptible to erosion). Soil had pH 7.2

Some characteristics of 11 entries screened under upland direct seeded situations, Krishnagar, India.

Designation	Height (cm)	Days to 50% flowering	Panicle length (cm)		Grain type ^a	Wt of single panicle (g)	Sheath blight score
			Mean	SD			
IR47701-79-B-14	94	75	20.0	1.36	MS	2.5	0
IR47701-79-B-1	93	73	24.6	2.16	MS	2.8	0
Milyang	91	67	15.0	1.25	SB	3.3	3
CNA4196	101	72	18.5	1.26	LS	3.7	5
IAC165	107	76	21.0	(0.16)	MS	3.7	0
CNA4746	104	68	20.5	1.32	LS	2.8	5
CNA4125	79	71	22.2	1.96	LB	1.8	5
GS529	110	67	23.0	1.21	LS	4.2	1
Dular (check)	99	67	19.5	2.31	MS	2.8	7
IET2223 (check)	93	75	23.0	1.27	MS	4.2	1
Rasi (check)	92	73	20.5	1.81	LB	3.0	6

^aMS = medium slender, SB = short bold, LS = long slender, LB = long bold.

and is deficient in N, organic matter, and phosphate. The crop was subjected to moisture stress at different growth stages, particularly during the seedling stage.

The experiment was laid out as a simple observational plot, with two 2-m rows/line (direct seeded), with 20 cm between rows.

Eight promising lines were identified

(see table). GS529 and Milyang have the same number of days to flowering as Dular, but GS529 has longer panicles and long slender grains, and is resistant to sheath blight. Panicle weight is high. Advanced breeding line RP47701-79-B-1, with 73 d to flowering and high resistance to sheath blight, is considered promising. □

Excess water tolerance

Promising breeding lines for submergence-prone and medium-deep rainfed lowland conditions

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We evaluated 209 rice breeding lines and local and improved cultivars under two water regimes in the field at IRRI. Cultivars for both trials were sown 27 Jun and transplanted 27 Jul 1988.

In trial 1, entries were submerged gradually to a 60-cm water level 45 d after sowing (DAS). Water depth was maintained for 12 d, then gradually brought down to 25 cm for the remainder of the season. In trial 2, entries were submerged suddenly to 60

cm at 50 DAS, water depth was maintained for 8 d, then brought down to less than 10 cm.

Plant height before and after flooding were measured (tip of the longest leaf)

and percent survival calculated. Elongation was calculated as the difference in height before and after flooding.

Survival was 24.9% for trial 1 and 36.7% for trial 2. In trial 1, the correlation between survival and initial plant height was low, but significant (*r*

Entries with the highest survival in 2 field tests of performance^a under submergence. IRRI, 1988 wet season.

Breeding line	Survival (%)		Elongation (cm)		Submergence tolerance ^b	Mature height ^c (cm)	Days to maturity ^d
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2			
IR49830-26-1-2-1	65	75	29	19	3.0	130	140
IR51052-2-3-1-6	70	68	—	—	9.0	140	135
IR6370-K23-1	85	58	—	—	9.0	120	SEN
IR51053-10-2-3-2	59	68	—	—	8.0	140	130
IR49830-29-1-3-3-2	58	65	12	15	1.0	140	130
IR43470-7-3-5-1	54	58	25	5	3.0	115	130
BKNFR76106-16 (R ck)	11	89	17	19	6.6	105	120
IR43522-37-3-3-3	55	43	27	20	8.2	140	SEN
IR42 (susceptible check)	0	0	—	—	8.5	105	135

^aTrial 1 = slow submergence, trial 2 = rapid submergence. ^bAverage scores from screenhouse screening in tanks, compared with tolerant check FR13A. ^cAverage of field data. ^dSEN = photoperiod sensitive.

= 0.30); the correlation of survival and elongation was highly significant ($r = 0.71$). Many tall plant types were able to escape flood through elongation.

In trial 2, the correlation of survival and initial plant height also was low ($r = 0.31$); survival was not correlated significantly with elongation ($r = -0.20$). Because tall types lack submergence

tolerance, they were unable to survive sudden inundation.

Many entries that performed well in one trial did poorly in the other (see table). Most of the entries with the best overall survival have shorter plant height, indicating that they survive from tolerance for submergence, not from

escape.

IR43470-7, IR49830-26, and IR49830-29 derive their submergence tolerance from the traditional cultivar FR13A. They have shown very high submergence tolerance in greenhouse screening at IRRRI and have a very good plant type. □

Adverse temperature tolerance

Screening rice seedlings for cold tolerance

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We screened 20 elite rice cultivars for cold tolerance at the seedling stage during 1988-89.

Uniform seeds, 50/entry with 2 replications, were soaked in water 24 h, washed repeatedly in distilled water, covered with moist tissue paper, and incubated at room temperature. After 3 d incubation, the seeds were transferred to glass containers with 3 cm water and kept at 4 °C. After 10 d of low temperature treatment, the containers were transferred to room temperature for 1 d.

Differences in seedling survival at low temperature were not significant. Based on seedling height, 16 entries showed tolerance for cold stress (see table).

Cold tolerance at early seedling stage of IET entries, based on seedling survival and seedling height. Tamil Nadu, India.

Entry	Seedling survival (%)	Seedling height (m)	Shoot/root ratio	Cold tolerance score ^b
IET 6786	54	8.0	0.9	3
IET 7261	76	10.2	0.7	1
IET 7589	56	13.3	0.7	1
IET 7946	78	10.3	0.6	1
IET 7988	50	13.1	0.9	1
IET 7989	50	14.3	0.9	1
IET 8024	76	13.8	0.8	1
IET 8101	78	12.0	1.1	1
IET 8626	58	8.9	0.7	3
IET 8866	81	11.4	1.3	1
IET 9202	79	13.2	0.8	1
IET 9315	62	12.3	0.9	1
IET 9797	57	9.3	0.5	3
IET 9802	58	12.8	0.9	1
IET 9815	64	11.0	0.7	1
IET 10358	56	12.7	0.8	1
IET 10385	70	12.7	0.8	1
IET 10505	69	12.7	0.8	1
IR46	60	11.7	1.1	1
MDU2 (control)	66	8.0	0.5	3

^a1 = all seedlings with green leaves, 3 = less than 30% of seedlings dead, 5 = 30-50% of seedlings dead, 7 = more than 50% seedlings dead, 9 = all seedlings dead. ^b1 = seedling height more than 10 cm, 3 = seedling height 8-10 cm, 5 = seedling height 5-7 cm, 7 = seedling height 3-4 cm, 9 = seedling height less than 1 cm.

Adverse soils tolerance

Effect of increased salinity on rice genotypes

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We compared the salt tolerance of hybrid NIAB-Rice-1 and mutants NIAB-Rice-3, RST-24, and BSRS-I-85 (derivatives of Basmati 370) with that of their parents Jhona 349 and Basmati 370.

Seedlings grown on a nonsaline field were transplanted at 45 d after sowing in concrete tanks (254 × 82 × 23 cm) filled with quartz gravel saturated with Hoagland nutrient solution. One seedling/hill per genotype was transplanted at 30- × 30-cm spacing. The experiment was in a randomized block design with six replications. Root zone EC levels of 2.4, 5.0, and 10.0